

The Dark Matter Scatter

How the Dark Universe Community is fraying, and in which directions, as a response to the DM crisis; How PEMC re-unifies the camps

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

January, 2019

ABSTRACT

Dark Matter has been in crisis for several years. Beginning in 2017, adherents began jumping ship with DM lifeboats, masquerading as both real science and classical Dark Matter. In previous parts the author discussed the predictable ‘Charged’ DM, the use of BEC (instead of ultracold plasmas), Dark (‘Hidden’) Photons, Negative Mass, and Neutrino radiation formed via Acoustic Shockwaves. In this paper, the absence of DM in the Milky Way and nearby galaxies, as well as other places, will be discussed alongside blatant misrepresentations (such as Dark Matter ‘glowing’), ultralight BEC’s, and by contrast DM “heating up”, which shows logical inconsistencies in DM theories. Contrasted with these disparate options, Plasma-Electromagnetism has a one-stop-shop for these observations with varying ranges of temperatures and behaviors which can describe all the matter, and repulsive forces without resorting to exotic (ie, ‘made up’) materials.

Keywords: Acoustic shockwaves - plasma - neutrinos - redshift - rearrangement

Where is the Dark Matter? Literally it isn't there.

The detraction from Lambda Cold Dark Matter (and DM in general) has always been “where is it?” In the 2000s, WMAP¹ and similar programs were used to create beautiful 3D models² with simulations of the Big Bang Expansion³, with Dark Matter inserted in purple (see Figure 1), as it was a reasonable standin given it was expected we would not ‘see’ DM or DE as they “do not interact with normal matter.”⁴ But while this is clever hand-waving, which was acceptable at the time, ahead of the opening of the Large Hadron Collider, it remained a viable critique. “Where is it?”

“Wait,” we were told, “until the LHC is up and running.”

Figure 1 - “DM” filaments in Virgo Supercluster; credit: Max Planck Institute

While the Higgs⁵ was found relatively quickly⁶, continuous funding and searching for CDM has not yielded anything, but has instead, produced a string of official failures and “constraints” (see Table 2).

Conversely, the filaments were found to contain strings of galaxies aligning impossibly end to end⁷, in similar vectors along their central axes.⁸ The dwarves of these galaxies were also found to rotate coplanar, rather than in disorganized gravitational fashion as expected.⁹

Solar Systems were found to be coplanar¹⁰, and all the disc galaxies of the Universe were found to rotate at the same rate,¹¹ which is impossible in thermonuclear dynamic explosions (as the Big Bang is supposed to have been).¹²

Starting in 2018, the question (frantically) became “Where is the Dark Matter?” when literally galaxies were being found that did not have any¹³ ¹⁴, or did not have “enough” (of the invisible material)¹⁵. Coincidentally, scores of alternative hypotheses emerged¹⁶, claiming pseudoscientific Dark Matter replacements¹⁷. Unironically, Gaia DR2 and MMS began returning data, and radio-scopes also corroborated

¹ https://www.ted.com/talks/george_smoot_on_the_design_of_the_universe/transcript?language=en

² <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2014/may/07/universe-recreated-computer-simulation-model-big-bang>

³ <https://www.sciencealert.com/most-advanced-illustris-next-generation-computer-model-universe-simulations>

⁴ <https://home.cern/science/physics/dark-matter>

⁵ <https://home.cern/science/physics/higgs-boson>

⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/blog/2012/jul/04/higgs-boson-discovered-live-coverage-cern>

⁷ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn26598-galaxies-in-filaments-spaced-like-pearls-on-a-necklace/>

⁸ http://www.star.bris.ac.uk/sxp/galaxiesnotes_short.pdf

⁹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1301.0446>

¹⁰

<http://curious.astro.cornell.edu/about-us/159-our-solar-system/the-sun/the-solar-system/236-are-the-planes-of-solar-systems-aligned-with-the-plane-of-the-galaxy-intermediate>

¹¹ <http://www.astronomy.com/news/2018/03/all-galaxies-rotate-once-every-billion-years>

¹² Should be radial and randomized, although in concentrations and wide gaps. But not structured.

¹³ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2018/03/dark-matter-galaxy-gravity-dragonfly-physics-space-science/>

¹⁴ Hilariously, one group tried to claim that the absence of something proved its existence, which is a logical fallacy.

¹⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.10714.pdf>

¹⁶ See [8],[10-12]

¹⁷ See [12]

which showed that half the matter was actually just baryons¹⁸, and the rest was likely “hot grains” or “local dust”, acting as so called “Covert Matter”¹⁹.

Dark Photons Must Be Making Dark Matter Glow with Ordinary Light

It is not without a small amount of vexation that the author finds the entire premise of recent research, claiming that X rays - which are ordinary EMF waves within the normal electromagnetic spectrum - are glowing due not to electromagnetic activity in an obviously charged plasma environment, but due to Dark Matter.²⁰ Obviously the charged dust and covert matter in the galaxy MACS J0416.1-2403 is undergoing a charging up process. See Figure 2 and Nasa’s subtitle below:

“Hubble’s powerful sensitivity and resolution captures a soft blue haze, called intracluster light, among innumerable galaxies in the Abell S1063 cluster. The stars producing this glow have been thrown out from their galaxies. These stars now live solitary lives, no longer part of a galaxy but aligning themselves with the gravity of the overall cluster. Astronomers have found that intracluster light’s association with a map of mass distribution in the cluster’s overall gravitational field makes it a good indicator of how invisible dark matter is distributed in the cluster.

Credits: NASA, ESA and M. Montes (University of New South Wales)” (sic)

The author finds this a tedious and ridiculous explanation. DM by definition is difficult to detect because it is not interacting with ordinary matter. To then claim it is, is pedantic.

Consider, as a comparison, the complete and total failure of the classical black hole model: “a singularity so dense with gravity so heavy that even light cannot escape it.” This is now considered totally fallacious.²¹ The author must point out that black holes have already been ruled out as the missing DM.²² But given that Crothers has already shown the classic black hole (and General Relativity as interpreted) to be fallacious, this isn’t very surprising. So why do they insist on using the term “black hole” when in fact tons of material²³, gas²⁴ (plasma²⁵), electric currents²⁶, and magnetic fields²⁷ are escaping these AGN Z-pinchs all the time?

Similarly, when one observes normal light, it’s a cinch that it is coming from explainable, normal electromagnetic interactions, albeit at high currents ($10^{18}+$ A) and extreme TeV charge densities (masses).²⁸

¹⁸ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2149742-half-the-universes-missing-matter-has-just-been-finally-found/>

¹⁹ see [8]

²⁰ <https://www.nasa.gov/image-feature/goddard/2018/faint-glow-within-galaxy-clusters-illuminates-dark-matter>

²¹ <https://news.psu.edu/story/552527/2018/12/20/research/beyond-black-hole-singularity>

²² <http://news.berkeley.edu/2018/10/02/black-holes-ruled-out-as-universes-missing-dark-matter/>

²³ <https://www.eso.org/public/news/eso1835/>

²⁴ <http://www.chandra.harvard.edu/photo/2018/a2597/>

²⁵ <https://alma-telescope.jp/en/news/press/blackhole-201812>

²⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.07327.pdf>

²⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.06025.pdf>

²⁸ See [6]. Table 7

Is it warming up, or is it really cold?

The following now truly encapsulates the confusion in the CDM community. See Figure 3, and included caption:

Figure 3: “Scientists have found evidence that dark matter can be heated up and moved around, as a result of star formation in galaxies. The findings provide the first observational evidence for the effect known as ‘dark matter heating’, and give new clues as to what makes up dark matter.” credit: Royal Astronomical Society²⁹

This type of iron-man hand-waving is truly disheartening. In actuality what the simulation shows is where gravity said, from WMAP measurements where DM **should be**. But not only are the concentrations completely wrong, they are wrong on the order of hundreds to thousands of parsecs.

What is heating up (in the past), likely are Birkeland Currents³⁰ (magnetic flux ropes), which are exchanging charges, such as baryons, along filaments *en masse* between clusters, galaxies, and ultimately heliospheres of stars.

“Gravitational potential fluctuations driven by bursty star formation can kinematically ‘heat up’ dark matter at the centres of dwarf galaxies. A key prediction of such models is that, at a fixed dark matter halo mass, dwarfs with a higher stellar mass will have a lower central dark matter density. We use stellar kinematics and HI gas rotation curves to infer the inner dark matter densities of eight dwarf spheroidal and eight dwarf irregular galaxies with a wide range of star formation histories. For all galaxies, we estimate the dark matter density at a common radius of 150 pc, $\rho_{DM}(150 \text{ pc})$. We find that our sample of dwarfs falls into two distinct classes. Those that stopped forming stars over 6 Gyrs ago favour central densities $\rho_{DM}(150 \text{ pc}) > 108 M_{\odot} \text{ kpc}^{-3}$, consistent with cold dark matter cusps, while

²⁹ <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/advance-article/doi/10.1093/mnras/sty3404/5265085>

³⁰ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2018/PP-53-01.PDF>

*those with more extended star formation favour $\rho_{DM}(150 \text{ pc}) < 108 M_{\odot} \text{ kpc}^{-3}$, consistent with shallower dark matter cores. Using abundance matching to infer pre-infall halo masses, M_{200} , we show that this dichotomy is in excellent agreement with models in which dark matter is heated up by bursty star formation. In particular, we find that $\rho_{DM}(150 \text{ pc})$ steadily decreases with increasing stellar mass-to-halo mass ratio, M_{\star}/M_{200} . Our results suggest that, **to leading order, dark matter is a cold, collisionless, fluid that can be kinematically ‘heated up’ and moved around.**³¹*

By definition, this is what plasma and superfluid Bose-Einstein Condensates (a proposed form of ultracold plasma) already do.

But, conversely to the idea of heating up:

*“Ultralight spin-less dark matter is one of the dark matter candidates that shows properties that suit the current observational restrictions. Among the convenient properties of this particle are that it is ultralight, with mass of order $m \sim 10^{-22} \text{ eV}$ [1–3], which implies it has a de Broglie wave-length that can prevent structures to develop cusps at the center of structures, which may be a solution of the cusp core problem [4–8]. At larger scales, there are now structure formation simulations showing that this candidate behaves just like CDM [9, 10]. Another problem possibly addressed by this candidate is the abundance of substructure [1–3, 5, 11]. Another appealing property is that a boson with such a small mass, **the critical temperature for Bose-Einstein condensation is $T_c \sim 1/m^5/3$ in the TeV scale**, which guarantees the condensation could have happened at very early stages.”³²³³*

Isn't it convenient that everyone gets to decide when their version of CDM exists, based upon as of yet unproven claims of the age of the Universe (based on poorly understood redshift, which has been shown to be well off (Table 2))? It's as if there are enough billions of years for everyone to create their own Dark Matter. And then, it can heat up and move around. These astrophysicists do realize they are working with still images that barely change in years of time, right? In the end, the measured filaments are a correction of previous guesses, which were made using data that was likely interfered with by the oceanic black body radiation of the Earth. When these corrections were made, suddenly it was found that Dark Matter was heating up, which is inconvenient, so why not say that *your* “Dark Matter” comes from later (6 Gyrs)? Why not have a whole rainbow of material no one can find, with different timestamps, so that if one is constrained out, it doesn't eliminate the entire scientific endeavor? After all, there are many more grants to acquire in constant pursuit of the mythical aether.

Real Consequences

There are, of course, several reasons why this is a monumentally bad idea. While the failure of CDM has not stopped the progress (indeed it has helped it) of the advance of plasma-electromagnetic cosmology, it is the less efficient way to exploring the issue.

Also, considering the transition to electrometerology³⁴, electrogeology³⁵, electrovolconology^{36 37}, electrocometology³⁸ (which has been slowed, but remains boosted by continual discovery of predicted

³¹ Ibid. Abstract

³² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.11612.pdf> p. 1

³³ See [11]

³⁴ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2018JD028489>

³⁵ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2018SW001880>

³⁶ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/news/189371/volcanoes-mush-reservoirs-rather-than-molten/>

³⁷ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/09/180904093838.htm>

³⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34wtt2EUToo>

dual-lobe comets and asteroids³⁹), it seems a bit of a hindrance for the rest of astronomy and astrophysics to remain in the *Dark Ages* (pun intended). After all, calls for the re-measuring of black holes have already gone out, new levels of radiation around Earth⁴⁰ and Saturn^{41 42} have been found⁴³ and all that remains is to tie this web of obvious electric current together with non-gravitationally based models which utilize magnetohydrodynamics, quantum electromechanics, superfluidity, high energy plasma physics, and new electromagnetism.⁴⁴

As the author mentioned in the later sections of “Magnetic Universe Theory,” there are several untapped sources (even unexplored) of charge flow that could more than solve humanity’s needs for electricity. If an oil executive was told that a totally untapped, massive, and inexhaustible source of crude oil was to be found, and all they needed was to go to a certain depth, they would spare no expense in research and development for acquiring that energy source. That makes sense at this current juncture. While it is barbaric, burning so-called fossil fuels provides cheap chemical energy which can be converted into mechanical advantage to create high tension power lines for general widespread use. The production of the lines and maintenance also provides countless jobs and need.

When Tesla and Steinmetz transformed the electric grid of the US and Europe, and eventually ushered in a new world of energy and connectivity, they never imagined, however, that we would stop and remain transfixed in the same system. Both would have expected us, by now, to have tapped into Birkeland’s sea of charge at the poles, and to wirelessly transmit the superfluid **real** aether all around the planet. Again, we know that 100,000- 650,000 A circulates above and around the Earth⁴⁵, in perpetuum, and that it is mostly being wasted. But despite this the sun actually will not run out of mass for billions of years⁴⁶, because the amount of mass it sheds yearly is miniscule to the current size (even without additional mass coming from the galaxy (GEC) or cluster (SGEC)).

So why are we not racing to develop this source? Leadership failures, pure and simple. Whether it is scientific leadership, or government comptrollers, funding of weak endeavors is bound to continue human dependence on fossil fuels, and also prolong the time which it takes for mankind to develop truly green power technology, which takes advantage of the free energy and charge in the atmosphere, space, and the high tension between the Earth and the moon.⁴⁷

As for current funding, this was covered in the first part of this series. But, more to the point, the amount of money that has been spent on the US nuclear program since 1940 far exceeds the investment costs which would be needed to explore this power production technology,⁴⁸ and also to explore other important avenues, such as the Changes - which have no substantive research at all.

Regardless, the DM community needs to straighten out its propositions and intentions. The scattered and seemingly desperate threads that are proposed seem more like cash grabs than realistic proposals. They certainly do not seem like empirical propositions with the best intentions and most honest observations. Rather, it seems like more attempts to uphold the house of cards that has become the Dark Universe, and by extension, Big Bang Cosmology.

³⁹ See: Ultima Thule <http://pluto.jhuapl.edu/News-Center/News-Article.php?page=20190101>

⁴⁰

http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/nph-iarticle_query?1983SSRv...34..223W&data_type=PDF_HIGH&whole_paper=YES&type=PRINTER&filetype=.pdf

⁴¹ <https://www.nasa.gov/press-release/goddard/2018/ring-rain>

⁴² <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?feature=7251>

⁴³ Not to fail to mention the proven connection of Earth’s water to Saturn, now (isotopes):

<https://phys.org/news/2018-12-saturn-satellites-earth-moon-phoebe.html>

⁴⁴ See [6], “R Distinti” & <http://www.distinti.com/docs/neThesis.pdf>

⁴⁵ [6]. Table 7

⁴⁶ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1KtbWKGILL0OP3sVbp0eNUuT06Ls3bJiA0gOkM21DRzM/edit?usp=sharing>

⁴⁷ See [14], pp. 110-125

⁴⁸ [5] p.2

Table 1 :: Proper Physics Chronology⁴⁹

Electricity	Ben Franklin	1751
Gaussian Theory	Carl Gauss	1813
Electromagnetism Unification	Michael Faraday	1831
Doppler Redshift	Hippolyte Fizeau	1848
Maxwell's Equations	James Maxwell	1861-62
Quantized Hypothesis	Ludwig Boltzmann	1877
Photoelectric effect	Heinrich Hertz	1887
Electron Theory	JJ Thomson	1897
Quantum Theory	Max Planck	1900
Relativity theory	Henri Poincare	1900-1904
Mass-energy relation	Henri Poincare	1900
Gravity Waves	Henri Poincare	1905
Special Relativity	Albert Einstein	1905
Photoelectric Effect Explained	Albert Einstein	1905
Birkeland Currents	Kristian Birkeland	1908
Atomic Theory Proved	Ernest Rutherford	1911
Particle-Wave Theory of Atoms and Particles	Niels Bohr	1913
General Relativity	Albert Einstein	1915
Proton discovered	Ernest Rutherford	1919
Quantum Radiation Interaction	Paul Dirac	1920
Quantum Mechanics Codified	Born, Heisenberg, Pauli	1924
Bose-Einstein Condensate	Bose, Einstein	1924
Plasma Cosmology	Irving Langmuir	1927
Big Bang Cosmology	Georges Lemaitre	1927
Missing Matter	Edward Zwicky	1933
Magnetohydrodynamics	Hannes Alfven	1940
QEM/QED	Bethe to Feynman	1947-1960
Electroweak Theory	JC Ward	1959
Quarks	M Gell-Mann & G Zweig	1964
Black Hole Theory	John Wheeler	1967
Dark Matter	Rubin & Ford	1970
Electric Star Theory	Ralph Juergens ⁵⁰	1972
QCD	Gross, Wilczek, & Politzer	1973
SUSY	Werner Nahm	1978
MOND	Mordehai Milgrom	1982-83
String Theory	Green & Schwarz	1984
Dark Energy	Friedman ⁵¹ or Sivaram ⁵²	1924 or 1986
M Theory	Edward Witten	1995
Intrinsic Redshift	Halton Arp ⁵³	1998
MACHOs	unclear	2002? ^{54 55}

⁴⁹ Tables 1 and 2 reproduced from [11]; all references in [13] included, as this paper is a follow-up.

⁵⁰ https://www.velikovsky.info/Ralph_Juergens

⁵¹ <http://home.fnal.gov/~skent/early.html>

⁵² <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0809/0809.3364.pdf>

⁵³ https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf

⁵⁴ <http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~george/ay20/ea-wimps-machos.pdf>

⁵⁵ <https://theconversation.com/from-machos-to-wimps-meet-the-top-five-candidates-for-dark-matter-51516>

Table 2 :: Falsifications

SUSY	2012 ⁵⁸ - 2017 ⁵⁹
CDM	2012 ⁶⁰ , 2015 ⁶¹ , 2016 ⁶² - 2018 ^{63 64 65 66}
ΛCDM	2010 ⁶⁷ , 2014 ⁶⁸
WIMPs & MACHOs	2017 ⁶⁹
MOND	2018 ^{70 71 72}
Galaxy Rotation and DM	2017 ^{73 74}
Standard Redshift	2017 ^{75 76 77}
Galaxy Rotation and MOND	2018 ⁷⁸
Higgs-boson as non-standard Quark	2018 ⁷⁹
Dark Energy	2018 ⁸⁰
LDM	2018 ⁸¹

Conclusion

Untapped sources of energy remain an important long-term discussion. But in the interim, as scientists scatter from the failing and failed Dark Matter paradigm, it will be necessary to qualify and quantify the data and bring it under the PEMC paradigm, to begin restoring previous evolution in science and humanity's standards of living. When EMF was discovered and made humanity's servant in the 1800's it led to massive change, and some of it was horrific. This, just as DM, was due to a misunderstanding of the meaning and value of what was found - the true Aether: charge. PEM is the true Unified Aether Field. However, DM scientists continue to be befuddled, or to create fantasies to prop up their grants and publish fancy mathematical papers, abusing that tool, and to no real benefit of mankind. Meanwhile, a completely new world of basically free,

⁵⁶ <https://www.astro.umd.edu/~ssm/darkmatter/WIMPexperiments.html>

⁵⁷ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/dark-matter-exotic-possibilities/>

⁵⁸ <http://backreaction.blogspot.com/2016/08/the-lhc-nightmare-scenario-has-come-true.html>

⁵⁹ <https://www.space.com/39001-dark-matter-doesnt-exist-study-suggests.html>

⁶⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2546>

⁶¹ http://adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/bib_query?arXiv:1406.4860

⁶² <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016arXiv161003854K>

⁶³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.09823.pdf>

⁶⁴ <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/476/3/3124/4875952>

⁶⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.07113.pdf>

⁶⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.04817.pdf>

⁶⁷ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0004>

⁶⁸ https://astro.uni-bonn.de/~pavel/kroupa_SciLogs.html

⁶⁹ <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-machos-dead-wimps-no-shows-simps.html>

⁷⁰ <https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/falsifications-and-constraints-due-to-gw-measurements.929254/>

⁷¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04167.pdf>

⁷² <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1809/1809.09019.pdf>

⁷³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.10706.pdf>

⁷⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08843.pdf>

⁷⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>

⁷⁶ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.09409>

⁷⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03888.pdf>

⁷⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1801.09304.pdf>

⁷⁹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06130-9>

⁸⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.05027.pdf>

⁸¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.10543.pdf>

untapped, endless energy awaits us. If only we would have the sense to stop the spending spree, and really invest in the proper Science.

References

1. "Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
http://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended-Plasma-Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC
2. "On the Origins of Religions," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
http://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions
3. "Unboxing Atlantis," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
http://www.academia.edu/36753644/Unboxing_Atlantis_A_top-down_review_of_what_we_know_and_dont_know_about_the_Atlantean_through_Megalithic_Period_continents_and_cities_36_000_-2_000_YBP
4. "Our Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
http://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma-Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow-Expanding-Growing-Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude
5. "Investments in Ragnarok," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
http://www.academia.edu/36753646/Investments_in_Ragnarok_Comparisons_and_Conclusions_from_the_study_of_Media_Business_and_Government_investments_in_End_of_the_World_myth_story_and_preparation
6. "Magnetic Universe Theory," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top-Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC
7. "Ferris Wheels and the Dionysian Irony," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
http://www.academia.edu/37403915/Ferris_Wheels_and_the_Dionysian_Irony_The_subconscious_drive_of_thrill_abandonment_of_caution_and_the_motifs_of_Amusement_Park_rides
8. "The Predictable Rise of 'Charged' Dark Matter," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328175179_The_Predictable_Rise_of_Charged_Dark_Matter_How_Covered_Matter_Hot_Grains-Plasma_in_Dark_Mode-is_pushing_the_failures_of_CDM_and_MOND_into_the_Plasma-Electromagnetic_Cosmological_Paradigm
9. "Clinical Electric Field Measurements," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328697566_Clinical_Electric_Field_Measurements_In_situ_pre_and_post_treatment_measurement_data_with_weather_and_space-weather_lunar_and_solar_data_with_self-reported_pain_and_significance_scales_in_three_phases
10. "Chinese Natural Philosophy (Physics) in EPEMC," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
http://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC
11. "Bose-Einstein Condensate Cosmology vs PEMC," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329427472_Bose-Einstein_Condensate_Cosmology_vs_PEMC_Cold_plasma_Discussing_the_problem_of_replacing_all_forms_of_Dark_Matter_with_an_interstellar_medium_BEC_vs_PEMUAF
12. "Pseudoscience Cannot be Dark Matter," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329629284_Pseudoscience_Cannot_Be_Dark_Matter_A_Short_Concise_Rebuttal_to_Negative_Mass_Dark_Photons_and_the_General_Bunkish_Trend_Physics_in_Crisis_Must_be_Guided_to_Safe_Shores
13. "Acoustic Shockwave Cosmology and EPEMC," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
https://www.academia.edu/38017260/Acoustic_Shockwave_Cosmology_Big_Bang_and_PEMC_The_belief_in_emergent_matter_versus_material_rearrangement
14. "Plasma Petroglyphs (Plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

15. "Charge Distribution Networks as Meridians," Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_'structure'_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models
16. "Bose-Einstein condensate," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bose%E2%80%93Einstein_condensate
17. "Bose-Einstein condensate in cosmology," S. Das and R. K. Bhaduri, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.10505.pdf>
18. "The Temperatures of Outer Space Around the Earth," A. Libal, 2018, <https://sciencing.com/temperatures-outer-space-around-earth-20254.html>
19. "The Matter- Antimatter asymmetry Problem," <https://home.cern/science/physics/matter-antimatter-asymmetry-problem>
20. "Did Gravity Save the Universe from 'God Particle' Higgs Boson?," C. Q. Choi, 2015, <https://www.space.com/28181-gravity-higgs-boson-universe-destruction.html>
21. "Higgs Boson," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Higgs_boson
22. "States of Matter: Bose-Einstein Condensate," J. Emspak, 2018, <https://www.livescience.com/54667-bose-einstein-condensate.html>
23. "Plasma classification (types of plasma)", [https://www.plasma-universe.com/Plasma_classification_\(types_of_plasma\)](https://www.plasma-universe.com/Plasma_classification_(types_of_plasma))
24. "Ultracold neutral plasmas," T.C. Killian et al., 2007, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0370157307001937?via%3Dihub>
25. "Trend: Ultracold Neutral Plasmas," S.L. Rolston, 2008, <https://physics.aps.org/articles/v1/2>
26. "Charged Planckian Interacting Dark Matter." M. Garnya, A. Palessandro et al...2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.01428.pdf>
27. "Nano dust in space and astrophysics," I. Mann et al..., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.12502.pdf>
28. "Measuring the local matter density using Gaia DR2," A. Widmark, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.07911.pdf>
29. "Discovery of a primordial water reservoir in the envelope of HH 211," O. Dionators, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08799.pdf>
30. "Half the universe's missing matter has just been finally found," New Scientist, L. Crane, 2017, <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2149742-half-the-universes-missing-matter-has-just-been-finally-found/>
31. "Discovery of massive warm-hot circumgalactic medium around NGC 3221," S Das et al..., 2018 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.12454.pdf>
32. "Universe has 2 trillion galaxies, astronomers say," The Guardian, 2016, <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2016/oct/13/hubble-telescope-universe-galaxies-astronomy>
33. "Y-Type Stars," Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory, 2017, <https://www.cfa.harvard.edu/news/su201725>
34. "Wasp-104B is darker than Charcoal," T. Mocnik, C. Hellier, and J. Southworth, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.05334.pdf>
35. "Origins of Hot Jupiters," R. Dawson & J. A. Johnson, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1801.06117>
36. "Ralph Juergens," The Velikovsky Encyclopedia, https://www.velikovskyy.info/Ralph_Juergens
37. "The Early History of Dark Energy," <http://home.fnal.gov/~skent/early.html>
38. "A Brief History of Dark Energy," C Sivaram, <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0809/0809.3364.pdf>
39. "Intrinsic Redshifts in Quasars and Galaxies," H. Arp et al...https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf
40. "WIMPs and MACHOs, Copyright © Nature Publishing Group 2002, K. Griest, <http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~george/ay20/ea-wimps-machos.pdf>
41. "Cold Dark Matter and Experimental Searches for WIMPs," <https://www.astro.umd.edu/~ssm/darkmatter/WIMPexperiments.html>
42. "From MACHOs to WIMPs: meet the top five candidates for 'dark matter'," The Conversation.com, 2015, <https://theconversation.com/from-machos-to-wimps-meet-the-top-five-candidates-for-dark-matter-51516>
43. S. Hossenfelder, The LHC "nightmare scenario" has come true," 2016, Available at <http://backreaction.blogspot.com/2016/08/the-lhc-nightmare-scenario-has-come-true.html>
44. "Does Dark Matter Exist? Bold New Study Offers Alternative Model," Tereza Pultarova, 2017, <https://www.space.com/39001-dark-matter-doesnt-exist-study-suggests.html>
45. "The dark matter crisis: falsification of the current standard model of cosmology," P. Kroupa, 2012, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2546>

46. "Galaxies as simple dynamical systems: observational data disfavor dark matter and stochastic star formation," Canadian Journal of Physics, vol. 93, P. Kroupa, 2015, http://adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/bib_query?arXiv:1406.4860
47. "The observed spatial distribution of matter on scales ranging from 100kpc to 1Gpc is inconsistent with the standard dark-matter-based cosmological models, P. Kroupa, 2016, <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016arXiv161003854K>
48. "Problems with The Dark Matter and Dark Energy: Hypothesis and alternative Ideas," M. L.. Corredoira, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.09823.pdf>
49. "Probing dark matter with star clusters: a dark matter core in the ultra-faint dwarf Eridanus II," Oxford Academic, F. Contenta et al., 2018, <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/476/3/3124/4875952>
50. "Search for annual and diurnal rate modulations in the LUX experiment , D.S. Akerib et al...., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.07113.pdf>
51. "Reply to the claim by van Dokkum et al. for a galaxy not containing dark matter .R.Scarpa et al..., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.04817.pdf>
52. "Simultaneous Falsification of LCDM and Quintessence with Massive, Distant Clusters," M.J. Mortonson, 2010, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0004>
53. "Pavel Kroupa: The Dark Matter Crisis," P. Kroupa, 2018, https://astro.uni-bonn.de/~pavel/kroupa_SciLogs.html
54. "MACHOs are dead. WIMPs are a no-show. Say hello to SIMPs: New candidate for dark matter," Phys.org., R. Sanders, 2017, <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-machos-dead-wimps-no-showsay-simps.html>
55. "Boran et al.,2017 "Falsifications and Constraints due to GW measurements," Available at <https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/falsifications-and-constraints-due-to-gw-measurements.929254/>
56. "MOND and the dynamics of NGC-1052-DF2," B. Famaey et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04167.pdf>
57. "No evidence for modifications of gravity From galaxy Motions on cosmological scales," J.He et al., <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1809/1809.09019.pdf>
58. "Investigating Dark Matter and MOND Models with Galactic Rotation Curve Data," M. T. Frandsen and J. Petersen, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.10706.pdf>
59. "The distribution of dark matter in galaxies," P Salucci, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08843.pdf>
60. "On the Gaia DR2 distances for Galactic Luminous Blue Variables," N. Smith et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>
61. "Detection of the gravitational redshift in the orbit of the star S2 near the Galactic centre massive black hole," R. Abuter et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.09409>
62. "EDGES result versus CMB and low-redshift constraints on ionization histories," S. Witte et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03888.pdf>
63. "Spiral Galaxy Rotation Curves Without Dark Matter or MOND – Two Conjectures," T. Biswas, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1801.09304.pdf>
64. "LHC physicists finally uncover Higgs 'bottom' decay," Nature International Journal of Science, D. Castelvechi, 2018, <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06130-9>
65. "Cherenkov radiation from the quantum vacuum," Macleod et al..., 2018 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.05027.pdf>
66. "Novel direct detection constraints on light dark matter," T. Bringmann & M. Pospelov, 2018 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.10543.pdf>
67. C. Harlos & T. Edgell, "We looked at 1,154 climate science results and found no evidence of 'publication bias," 2017, Available at <https://theconversation.com/we-looked-at-1-154-climate-science-results-and-found-no-evidence-of-publication-bias-84500>
68. "Climate Change Research Grants." US EPA, <https://www.epa.gov/research-grants/climate-change-research-grants>
69. "Publication bias in climate-change science," Lund University, <https://www.biology.lu.se/research/research-groups/aquatic-ecology/research-projects/publication-bias-in-climate-change-science>
70. H. Ludwig, "Your Tax Dollars Fund the 'Global Warming' Narrative," 2017, Available at <https://capitalresearch.org/article/your-tax-dollars-fund-the-global-warming-narrative/>

71. "Why Exploring Space And Investing In Research Is Non-Negotiable," Forbes, E. Siegel, 2017, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/startswithabang/2017/10/26/even-while-the-world-suffers-investing-in-science-is-non-negotiable/#1800d3dc1647>
72. "How much money is spent on space exploration? (Intermediate)," K. Masters, 2015, <http://curious.astro.cornell.edu/about-us/150-people-in-astronomy/space-exploration-and-astronauts/general-questions/921-how-much-money-is-spent-on-space-exploration-intermediate>
73. "The jets of AGN as giant coaxial cables," D. C. Gabuzda, 2017, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>
74. "Origin of Enigmatic Galactic-center Filaments Revealed," Y.-Zadeh, et al. 2004, <https://public.nrao.edu/news/origin-of-enigmatic-galactic-center-filaments-revealed/#PRImageSelected>
75. "The Io Dynamo," NASA, <https://www.spo.gsfc.nasa.gov/Education/wio.html>
76. "Magnetic Portals Connect Earth to the Sun," NASA, 2008, https://science.nasa.gov/science-news/science-at-nasa/2008/30oct_ftes
77. "Thin current sheets in space: where the action is," Swedish Institute of Space Physics, 2012, <https://phys.org/news/2012-08-thin-current-sheets-space-action.html>
78. "Current Sheets in the Solar Corona," The Astrophysical Journal, H. R. Strauss and N. F. Otani, © 1988, http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/nph-iarticle_query?1988ApJ...326..418S&data_type=PDF_HIGH&:whole_paper=YES&type=PRINTER&filetype=.pdf
79. "Collapse of neutral current sheet and reconnection at micro-scales," I. F. Shaikhislamov, <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1711/1711.11284.pdf>
80. "Current Sheet Formation in the Interstellar Medium," E. G Zweibel & A. Brandenburg, The Astrophysical Journal, 1997, <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/303824/pdf>
81. "Freezing-in condition for a magnetic field and current sheets in plasma," Astrophysics and Space Science, vol. 56, 1978, S. I. Syrovatskii, <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1978Ap%26SS..56....3S>
82. "Giant galaxy-packed filament revealed," McGill University, 2012, <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2012/05/120517143639.htm>
83. "Cosmic filament probes our galaxy's giant black hole," Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, 2017, <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-cosmic-filament-probes-galaxy-giant.html>
84. "Giant Dark Matter Bridge Between Galaxy Clusters Discovered," Space.com C. Moskowitz, 2012, <https://www.space.com/16412-dark-matter-filament-galaxy-clusters.html>
85. "Solar-radiation burst hit Earth in record time," K. Young, New Scientist, 2005, <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn7427-solar-radiation-burst-hit-earth-in-record-time/>
86. N. Mortillaro, CBC News, 2017 "7 Earth-sized planets found orbiting star 39 light-years away," Available at <https://www.cbc.ca/news/technology/7-earth-like-planets-discovered-1.3992156>
87. "How Cold Is a Y Dwarf Star? Even You Are Warmer," C. Q. Choi, 2011, <https://www.space.com/12714-coldest-failed-stars-brown-dwarfs-wise.html>
88. "Star smaller than Jupiter discovered," Space, 2017, <http://www.eniscuola.net/en/2017/07/18/star-smaller-jupiter-discovered/>
89. "Fast-spinning neutron star smashes speed limit," New Scientist, M. McKee, 2006, <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn8576-fast-spinning-neutron-star-smashes-speed-limit/>
90. "Observations challenge cosmological theories," University/Bonn, 2018, <https://www.uni-bonn.de/news/272-2018>
91. "Red face Shift," Everything Electric, 2015, <http://www.everythingelectric.com/red-face-shift/>
92. "First observation of gravitational waves," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/First_observation_of_gravitational_waves
93. "Gravitational Waves Detected from Neutron-Star Crashes: The Discovery Explained," C.Q. Choi, 2017, <https://www.space.com/38471-gravitational-waves-neutron-star-crashes-discovery-explained.html>
94. "Gravitational waves from a binary black hole merger observed by LIGO and Virgo," LIGO, 2017, <https://www.ligo.caltech.edu/news/ligo20170927>
95. "Virgo Joins LIGO in Detection of Gravitational Waves," APS Physics, D. Voss, 2017, <https://www.aps.org/publications/apsnews/updates/ligo-virgo.cfm>
96. "Stability of disks in quasilinear MOND," I. Banik et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.10545.pdf>
97. "Henri Poincaré, Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henri_Poincar%C3%A9#Three-body_problem
98. "Hubble data indicate universe growing faster than expected," Astronomy Now, W. harwood, 2018, <https://astronomynow.com/2018/02/23/hubble-data-indicate-universe-growing-faster-than-expected/>

99. "We may have Overestimated the Expansion rate of the Universe," Science, J. Walker, 2015, <http://www.digitaljournal.com/science/the-expansion-of-the-universe-may-be-much-slower-than-we-thought/article/430558>
100. "Faster Than Light? Neutron-Star Merger Shot Out a Jet with Seemingly Impossible Speed," Space, M. Wall, 2018, <https://www.space.com/41724-neutron-star-merger-superfast-jet.html>
101. "The Painlevé-Gullstrand 'Extension' - A Black Hole Fallacy," American Journal of Modern Physics, S. J. Crothers, 2016, <http://vixra.org/pdf/1512.0089v1.pdf>
102. "Thousands of Black Holes May Lurk at the Galaxy's Center," Nat Geo, S. Gibbens, 2018, <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2018/04/black-hole-stellar-binary-stars-milky-way-galaxy/>
103. "Gravitational Waves Could Collide Sucking Earth Into a Black Hole," Newsweek, K. Gander, 2018, <https://www.newsweek.com/gravitational-waves-could-collide-sucking-earth-black-hole-1097203>
104. "Does Dark Matter Ever Die?" PBS/KET, K. Becker, 2018, <http://www.pbs.org/wgbh/nova/next/physics/dynamical-dark-matter/>
105. "The frustrating and fascinating world of dark matter research," ScienceNordic, N. G. Nielsen, 2018, <https://phys.org/news/2018-03-frustrating-fascinating-world-dark.html>
106. K. Haynes, "What is Dark Matter..., Even the Best Theories are Crumbling," 2018, Available on <http://blogs.discovermagazine.com/crux/2018/09/21/the-dark-matter-crisis/#.W7u0CGhKjct>
107. "Yes, The Multiverse Is Real, But It Won't Fix Physics," E. Siegel, 2018, <https://medium.com/starts-with-a-bang/yes-the-multiverse-is-real-but-it-wont-fix-physics-82beaed322b>
108. "Variations Between Dust and Gas In The Diffuse Interstellar Medium 3. Changes In Dust Properties," W. T. Reach et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.03316.pdf>
109. "Hall effect-driven formation of gravitationally unstable discs in magnetized molecular cloud cores," J. Wurster et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.04376.pdf>
110. "21-cm Fluctuations from Charged Dark Matter," J. B. Muñoz, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1804.01092>
111. "Does Some Dark Matter Carry an Electric Charge?" Harvard Smithsonian CFA, 2018, <https://www.cfa.harvard.edu/news/2018-08>
112. "On the loadstone and magnetic bodies and on the great magnet the earth. A new physiology, demonstrated with many arguments and experiments," W. Gilbert, 1893, <https://archive.org/details/williamgilbertof00gilb/page/n5>
113. "Birkeland current," Wiki, https://www.plasma-universe.com/Birkeland_current
114. "Perspectives on Plasma," <http://www.plasmas.org/fusion-icf.htm>
115. "How to Register a Trademark for a Company Name," WSJ, <http://guides.wsj.com/small-business/starting-a-business/how-to-trademark-a-company-name/>
116. Radboud University, Astrophysics, "New theory explains missing Dark energy and Dark matter in our Universe." J.S. Farnes, 2018, <https://www.ru.nl/astrophysics/news-agenda/news/news-ru/new-theory-explains-missing-dark-energy-dark/>
117. "On the Gaia DR2 distances for Galactic Luminous Blue Variables," N. Smith et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>
118. "Intrinsic Redshifts in Quasars and Galaxies." H.Arp et al., https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf
119. Astronomy and Astrophysics, "Disk stars in the Milky Way detected beyond 25 kpc from its center," M.L. Corredoira et al., 2018, <https://www.aanda.org/articles/aa/abs/2018/04/aa32880-18/aa32880-18.html>
120. Astronomy and Astrophysics, "Measuring the local matter density using Gaia DR2," A. Widmark, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.07911.pdf>
121. Department of Astrophysics, University of Vienna, "Discovery of a primordial water reservoir in the envelope of HH 211," O. Dionatos, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08799.pdf>
122. Edge.org., "Crisis at the Foundation of Physics," S. Giddings, <https://www.edge.org/response-detail/23857>
123. Nature, "How the belief in beauty has triggered a crisis in physics," A. Ananthaswamy, 2018, <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-05374-9>
124. Pierre-Marie Robitaille, Articles/Abstracts List, http://vixra.org/author/pierre-marie_robitaille
125. Science & Invention (August 1929) / Psychic Observer 37, "How I Control Gravitation" T.T. Brown, http://blog.lege.net/content/Gravitator_1926.pdf
126. Biefeld-Brown Effect, Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Biefeld%E2%80%93Brown_effect

127. ScienceDirect, Physics Letter B Volume 787, "Search for dark matter in the form of hidden photons and axion-like particles in the XMASS detector," 2018, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0370269318308219?via%3Dihub#fn0030>
128. "What is the Mass of a Photon, M. Austern, http://math.ucr.edu/home/baez/physics/ParticleAndNuclear/photon_mass.html
129. "Does Light Have Mass?" P. Gibbs, 1997, http://www.desy.de/user/projects/Physics/Relativity/SR/light_mass.html
130. Darkstar Publications, "Uncovering the missing Secrets of Magnetism," K.L. Wheeler, 2014, <https://archive.org/details/magnetism1small/page/n13>
131. Quora, "What is Precisely the Speed of Light in Fiber Optics?" <https://www.quora.com/What-is-precisely-the-speed-of-light-in-fiber-optics>
132. "Intrinsic and extrinsic properties," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intrinsic_and_extrinsic_properties
133. ResearchGate, "Is LIGO guilty of Scientific Fraud? O. E. Rossler, 2015, https://www.researchgate.net/post/Is_LIGO_guilty_of_Scientific_Fraud
134. "The 2017 Nobel Prize for physics was awarded to a FRAUD," D. Chakalov, 2017. <http://vixra.org/pdf/1712.0017v1.pdf>
135. "Matter Emerges - A Group Project Proposal," W. R. Giordano, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37980100/Matter_Emerges_-_A_Group_Project_Proposal
136. "Tired Light," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tired_light
137. Ask an Astronomer, "Can "tired light theory" explain the observed redshifts of galaxies? (Intermediate) K. Masters, 2015, <http://curious.astro.cornell.edu/about-us/110-the-universe/cosmology-and-the-big-bang/alternate-theories/670-can-tired-light-theory-explain-the-observed-redshifts-of-galaxies-intermediate>
138. "Errors in Tired Light Cosmology," E.L. Wright, 2008, <http://www.astro.ucla.edu/~wright/tiredlit.htm>
139. "Tired Light and Type Ia Supernovae Observations," H. Holushko, <http://bourabai.kz/articles/snt.pdf>
140. "Time Dilation in Type Ia Supernova Spectra at High Redshift," S. Blondin et al., 2008, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0804.3595.pdf>
141. "Spiral Galaxy Rotation Curves Without Dark Matter or MOND – Two Conjectures," T. Biswas, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1801.09304.pdf>
142. "The Expanding Universe and Hubble's Law," https://www.physicsoftheuniverse.com/topics_bigbang_expanding.html
143. "Relativistic Jets in Active Galactic Nuclei," R. Blandford , D. Meier , and A. Readhead, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.06025.pdf>
144. "Michelson–Morley experiment," Wiki, https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Michelson%E2%80%93Morley_experiment
145. "Galactic - Scale Electric Fields Could Solve Dark Matter Mystery" 2014, <https://medium.com/the-physics-arxiv-blog/galactic-scale-electric-fields-could-solve-the-dark-matter-mystery-says-physicist-117a6488ba0e>
146. "A galaxy lacking dark matter," P.V. Dokkum et al., 2018, <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature25767>
147. "All disk galaxies rotate once every billion years," J. Parks, 2018, <http://www.astronomy.com/news/2018/03/all-galaxies-rotate-once-every-billion-years>
148. "Birkeland Currents," 2015, <http://www.everythingselectric.com/birkeland-currents/>
149. "Constraining the charge of the Galactic centre black hole, M.I Zajaček1 et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.03574.pdf>
150. "Detection of the gravitational redshift in the orbit of the star S2 near the Galactic centre massive black hole," GRAVITY collaboration, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.09409>
151. "New Simulation Sheds Light on Spiraling Supermassive Black Holes," J. Kazmierczak, 2018, <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2018/new-simulation-sheds-light-on-spiraling-supermassive-black-holes>
152. "Cloudlets Swarm Around our Local Supermassive Black Hole," 2018, <https://www.almaobservatory.org/en/audiences/cloudlets-swarm-around-our-local-supermassive-black-hole/>
153. "Black Hole 'Donuts' are Actually 'Fountains,'" 2018, <https://alma-telescope.jp/en/news/press/agn-201811>
154. "Cosmic Fountain Powered by Giant Black Hole," 2018, <http://www.chandra.harvard.edu/photo/2018/a2597/>

155. "Measurement of the Electric Current in a kpc Scale Jet," P. P. Kronberg et al., 2011, <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2041-8205/741/1/L15/pdf>
156. "The jets of AGN as giant coaxial cables," D. C. Gabuzda, M. Nagle and N. Roche, 2017, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>
157. "Birkeland Currents: A Force-Free Field-Aligned Model," D.E. Scott, 2015, <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>
158. "Electric Universe: has there ever been a scientific research program?" <http://www.internationalskeptics.com/forums/showthread.php?s=a6a26562dfa9ead7772d677dbad6a74d&t=302933&page=3&styleid=50>
159. "Accelerating expansion of the universe," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accelerating_expansion_of_the_universe
160. "Spin Physics," Wiki, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Spin_\(physics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Spin_(physics))
161. "Quantum gas goes below absolute zero, Ultracold atoms pave way for negative-Kelvin materials." Z. Merali, 2013, <https://www.nature.com/news/quantum-gas-goes-below-absolute-zero-1.12146>
162. Physics Stack Exchange, "[What are the calculations for Vacuum Energy?](https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/22468/what-are-the-calculations-for-vacuum-energy)" 2012, <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/22468/what-are-the-calculations-for-vacuum-energy>
163. The Guardian, "Universe recreated in massive computer simulation," I. Sample, 2014, <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2014/may/07/universe-recreated-computer-simulation-model-big-bang>
164. Science Alert, "Astrophysicists Have Built The Most Detailed Simulation of The Universe Ever Created" M. Mcrae, 2018, <https://www.sciencealert.com/most-advanced-illustris-next-generation-computer-model-universe-simulations>
165. CERN, (Science), "Dark Matter," <https://home.cern/science/physics/dark-matter>
166. CERN, (Science), "The Brout-Englert-Higgs Mechanism," <https://home.cern/science/physics/higgs-boson>
167. The Guardian News Blog, "Higgs boson announcement: Cern scientists discover subatomic particle," 2012, <https://www.theguardian.com/science/blog/2012/jul/04/higgs-boson-discovered-live-coverage-cern>
168. NewScientist, "Galaxies in filaments spaced like pearls on a necklace," L. Kruesi, 2014, <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn26598-galaxies-in-filaments-spaced-like-pearls-on-a-necklace/>
169. "Galaxies," Prof S. Phillipps, 2009, http://www.star.bris.ac.uk/xsp/galaxiesnotes_short.pdf
170. Nature, "A Vast Thin Plane of Co-rotating Dwarf Galaxies Orbiting the Andromeda Galaxy," R.A. Ibata et al., 2013, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1301.0446>
171. Ask an Astronomer, "Are the planes of solar systems aligned with the plane of the Galaxy? (Intermediate), C. Springob, 2015, <http://curious.astro.cornell.edu/about-us/159-our-solar-system/the-sun/the-solar-system/236-are-the-planes-of-solar-systems-aligned-with-the-plane-of-the-galaxy-intermediate>
172. Astronomy, "All disk galaxies rotate once every billion years" J. Parks, 2018, <http://www.astronomy.com/news/2018/03/all-galaxies-rotate-once-every-billion-years>
173. National Geographic, "This Galaxy Has Almost No Dark Matter—and Scientists Are Baffled," N. Drake, 2018, <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2018/03/dark-matter-galaxy-gravity-dragonfly-physics-space-science/>
174. "On the absence of dark matter in dwarf galaxies surrounding the Milky Way," F. Hammer et al., 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.10714.pdf>
175. New Scientist, "Half the Universe's Missing Matter has Just Been Found," L. Crane, 2017, <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2149742-half-the-universes-missing-matter-has-just-been-finally-found/>
176. NASA, "Faint Glow Within Galaxy Clusters Illuminates Dark Matter," L.Ramsay and R. Villard, 2018, <https://www.nasa.gov/image-feature/goddard/2018/faint-glow-within-galaxy-clusters-illuminates-dark-matter>
177. Penn State, "Beyond the Black Hole Singularity," S. Sholtis, 2018, <https://news.psu.edu/story/552527/2018/12/20/research/beyond-black-hole-singularity>
178. UC Berkeley, "Black holes ruled out as universe's missing dark matter," R. Sanders, 2018, <https://news.berkeley.edu/2018/10/02/black-holes-ruled-out-as-universes-missing-dark-matter/>
179. ESO, "Most Detailed Observations of Material Orbiting close to a Black Hole," GRAVITY collaboration, <https://www.eso.org/public/news/eso1835/>
180. ALMA, "Mystery of coronae around supermassive black holes deepens," 2018, <https://alma-telescope.jp/en/news/press/blackhole-201812>

181. "On the charge of the Galactic centre black hole," M. Zajačcek et al., 2018,
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.07327.pdf>
182. "Relativistic Jets in Active Galactic Nuclei," R. Blandford , D. Meier , and A.Readhead 2018,
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.06025.pdf>
183. Oxford Academic, " Dark matter heats up in dwarf galaxies," J. I. Read, M. G.Walker and P. Steger, 2019,
<https://academic.oup.com/mnras/advance-article/doi/10.1093/mnras/sty3404/5265085>
184. Progress in Physics, "Birkeland Currents and Dark Matter," D.E. Scott, 2018,
<http://www.ptep-online.com/2018/PP-53-01.PDF>
185. "Oscillation modes of ultralight BEC dark matter cores," F. S. Guzman, 2019,
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.11612.pdf>
186. AGU100, " Earthquake Lights: Mechanism of Electrical Coupling of Earth's Crust to the Lower Atmosphere," J. Jansky and V. P. Pasko, 2018, <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2018JD028489>
187. AGU100, " Geomagnetically Induced Currents Caused by Interplanetary Shocks With Different Impact Angles and Speeds," D. M. Oliveira, 2018, <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2018SW001880>
188. Imperial College London, "Volcanoes fed by 'mush' reservoirs rather than molten magma chambers," H. Dunning, 2018, <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/news/189371/volcanoes-mush-reservoirs-rather-than-molten/>
189. Science Daily, " New imagery solves mystery of why Mount St. Helens is out of line with other volcanoes," Oregon State University (source,) 2018, <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/09/180904093838.htm>
190. "The Earth's Ring Current: Causes Generation and Decay," D. J. Williams,
http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/nph-iarticle_query?1983SSRv...34..223W&data_type=PDF_HIGH&whole_paper=YES&type=PRINTER&filetype=.pdf
191. NASA, "NASA Research Reveals Saturn is Losing Its Rings at "Worst-Case-Scenario" Rate," 2018,
<https://www.nasa.gov/press-release/goddard/2018/ring-rain>
192. NASA, "Groundbreaking Science Emerges from Ultra-Close Orbits of Saturn," 2018,
<https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?feature=7251>
193. Phys.org., "The water in Saturn's rings and satellites is like that on Earth except for moon Phoebe, which is out of this world," 2018, <https://phys.org/news/2018-12-saturn-satellites-earth-moon-phoebe.html>
194. "Inductance Modeling Using New Electromagnetism," R.J. Distini, 2007,
<http://www.distinti.com/docs/neThesis.pdf>